

VERB RELATIONS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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Abstract:

The following article examines the types of verb tenses in Uzbek and English and explains their differences and uses. The main content of the article will help students learning English as a second foreign language to fully understand the meaning of verb ratios in both languages.

Key words: verb ratios, active voice, passive voice, suffix, tenses.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/zhq1ba69>

It is known that not knowing the mother tongue is foreign learning a language is a difficult matter. Because every language has its own grammar and to learn it, we must have some knowledge of the grammar of our mother tongue demand the various similarities and differences between them make people even more calls for deeper research. This phenomenon is similar to other languages such as Uzbek and English on their tongues. An example of this is a small grammar we can get verb proportions. Come rate now we will talk about its place in Uzbek and English languages. depends on the definition of ratios Let's face it. Fetl ratio is the action and the state of the person who performs this process indicates the degree to which he participated in the implementation. There are five types of verb ratios in the Uzbek language. In English they are of three types consists of the first of them is the exact ratio, which is also called the basic ratio. In this the action is performed by the person or thing that is the owner of the action sentence.

“Boysarining bu holini bilgan o‘zbek xabar olar”, — deb Surxayil kampir ham poyloqchilik qilib davrini suraverdi. [2;18]

I, at that distance, know what it was. I found quickly the negroes were for eating the flesh. [3; 20]

Exact Aspect Ratio - The performer accurately represents the action and does not add aspect ratio. Such o makes almost no difference in this ratio (aniq nisbat) [Erkaboyeva. N; 49] In Uzbek and English verbs, the verb to know and bilmoq means an action in which the executor is clearly defined.

Nigora gulni uzish uchun egildi. [5; 76]

The next type of relation is the self is a ratio, and the action is performed on the person or things themselves. That is, when the person performing the action and the object of the action are united will be. In Uzbek, the personal relation is formed by adding -n, -in, -l, -il to the verb.

Nigora went down to pick up the flower. [5; 77]

But there is no such ratio in English, and it is expressed by the ratio definite and comes as participle.

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Ayol ovqatni ichar ichmas qo'zg'aldi. Munavvarxonimning ko'ngli xotirjam edi. Kerakli saboq berildi. [1; 25]

It was given up, as above; which, as he remember, was for about twelve years. [3;154]

In Uzbek language by adding the adjuncts of this ratio type just like a proper ratio is formed. Since the personal and passive participles are the same, they are we differentiate by putting the word "himself" in front of it.

In English this is called passive voice and it is done with these formulas and tenses to be + V (3) or (ed).

“Sizlar ketaveringlar”, — deb tayinlab, o‘zlari jang qilish niyatida ortga qaytishdi. [2;16]

Nigora and Noila went to the theater. [6; 84]

The next ratio is the ratio of unity, the action or state of several people In the Uzbek language, this ratio is a work action performed by several persons It is formed by -sh (ish) adding suffixes

As mentioned above, the verb "went" is expressed in a definite proportion

Hech kimga bildirmay ikki kunda kelinni keltirdilar. [1; 39]

The last type of ratio is the additive ratio, which changes depending on the movement serves as a personal tool, that is, one person invites another person to Da'wah In the Uzbek language, this type of ratio is expressed by the suffixes - t, - ir, - iz, - sot, - dir, - tir, - giz, - kar is made.

We are going to have our meal cooked now. [4; 39]

In English, this type of Causative voice is formed in the verb "have something done".

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